

On a Subclass of Harmonic Univalent Functions Defined by Using a New Differential Operator

N.D. Sangle¹, A.N. Metkari,^{2,*} S.P. Hande³

¹Department of Mathematics, D.Y. Patil College of Engineering and Technology,
Kasaba Bawada, Kolhapur, Maharashtra 416006, India,

² Hon. Annasaheb Dange Junior College, Ashta, Maharashtra 416301, India,

³ Department of Mathematics, Vishwanathrao Deshpande Institute of Technology,
Haliyal, Karnataka 581329, India

*Corresponding Author: anand.metkari@gmail.com

Abstract In this paper, a class of complex-valued harmonic univalent functions $f(z) = h(z) + \overline{g(z)}$ in the open disk $U = \{z : z \in C \text{ and } |z| < 1\}$ is defined by using a new differential operator. We investigate coefficient bounds, distortion inequalities, extreme points and convex combination results for this class.

Subject Classification 30C45, 30C50.

Keywords Keywords: Harmonic functions, univalent functions and differential operator.

I Introduction

Harmonic functions are famous for their use in the study of minimal surfaces and also play important roles in a variety of problems in applied mathematics for this see [3], [5], [6]. A continuous function $f = u + iv$ is a complex valued harmonic function in a complex domain C if both u and v are real harmonic in C . In any simply connected domain $D \subseteq C$ we can write $f(z) = h(z) + \overline{g(z)}$, where h and g are analytic in D . We call h the analytic part and g the co-analytic part of f . A necessary and sufficient condition for f to be locally univalent and sense-preserving in D is that $|h'(z)| > |g'(z)|$ in D ; for this see [4].

Denote by S_H the class of functions $f(z) = h(z) + \overline{g(z)}$ that are harmonic univalent and sense-preserving in the unit disk $U = \{z : z \in C \text{ and } |z| < 1\}$ for which $f(0) = f_z(0) - 1 = 0$. Then for $f(z) = h(z) + \overline{g(z)} \in S_H$, we may express the analytic functions h and g as

$$h(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^k, \quad g(z) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k z^k, \quad z \in U. \tag{1}$$

Therefore

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^k + \overline{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k z^k}, \quad |b_1| < 1.$$

Note that S_H reduces to the class S normalized analytic univalent functions in U if the co-analytic part of f is identically zero.

In [4] investigated the class S_H as well as its geometric subclasses and obtained some coefficient bounds. Since then, there has been several related papers on H and its subclasses such as [1], [10], [11], [7] and [9] studied the harmonic univalent functions.

The differential operator $D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$) was introduced in [2]. For $f(z) = h(z) + g(\bar{z})$ given by (1), [12] defined the differential operator as

$$D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z) = D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)h(z) + (-1)^n \overline{D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)g(z)}$$

where

$$D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)h(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k$$

and

$$D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)g(z) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n b_k z^k,$$

where, $\mu, \lambda, w \geq 0, 0 \leq \alpha \leq \mu w^\lambda$, with $D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(0) = 0$.

The generalization of the differential operator for a function $f(z) = h(z) + g(\bar{z})$ given by (1).

$$D_{\alpha,\mu}^0(\lambda, w)f(z) = D^0 f(z) = h(z) + g(z),$$

$$D_{\alpha,\mu}^1(\lambda, w)f(z) = (\alpha - \mu w^\lambda) \left(h(z) + \overline{g(z)} \right) + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 1) \left(zh'(z) - \overline{zg'(z)} \right),$$

In general,

$$D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z) = D \left(D_{\alpha,\mu}^{n-1}(\lambda, w)f(z) \right). \tag{2}$$

If f is given by (1), then from (2), we see that

$$D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \overline{b_k z^k}. \tag{3}$$

When, $w = \alpha = 0$, we get modified Salgean differential operator [8].

We define $S_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ the subclass of S_H consisting of functions f of the form (1) that satisfy the condition

$$Re \left\{ (1 + e^{it}) \frac{D_{\alpha,\mu}^{n+1}(\lambda, w)f(z)}{D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z)} - e^{it} \right\} \geq \beta, \tag{4}$$

where, $D_{\alpha, \mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z)$ is defined by (3) and $(0 \leq \beta < 1, t \in R, n, \alpha \in N_0)$.

We let the subclass $\overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ consisting of harmonic functions $f_n = h + \overline{g}_n$ in S_H so that h and g_n are of the form.

$$h(z) = z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^k, \quad g_n(z) = (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k z^k, \quad a_k, b_k \geq 0 \tag{5}$$

The objective of the present paper is to give sufficient condition for functions $f = h + \overline{g}$ where h and g are given by (1) to be in the class $S_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ and it is shown that this coefficient condition is also necessary for functions belonging to the subclass $\overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$. Also, we obtain coefficient bounds, distortion inequalities, extreme points and convex combination results for this class.

II Coefficient Bounds

In our first theorem, we introduce a sufficient coefficient bound for harmonic functions in $S_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$.

Theorem II.1 Let $f = h + \overline{g}$ be so that h and g are of the form (1). Furthermore, let

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \{ [2((k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \} |a_k| \\ & + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \{ [2((k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \} |b_k| \\ & \leq (1 - \beta), \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

where $\mu, \lambda, w \geq 0, 0 \leq \alpha \leq \mu w^\lambda, t \in R, n \in N_0, 0 \leq \beta < 1$. Then f is sense-preserving, harmonic univalent in U and $f \in S_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$.

Proof: If $z_1 \neq z_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{f(z_1) - f(z_2)}{h(z_1) - h(z_2)} \right| & \geq 1 - \left| \frac{g(z_1) - g(z_2)}{h(z_1) - h(z_2)} \right| \\ & = 1 - \left| \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_k (z_1^k - z_2^k)}{(z_1 - z_2) + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k (z_1^k - z_2^k)} \right| \\ & > 1 - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k |b_k|}{1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k |a_k|} \\ & \geq 1 - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n |b_k|}{1 - \beta}}{1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n |a_k|}{1 - \beta}} \\ & \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Which proves univalence. Note that f is sense preserving in U . This is because

$$\begin{aligned}
 |h'(z)| &\geq 1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k |a_k| |z|^{k-1} \\
 &> 1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} |a_k| \\
 &\geq \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} |b_k| \\
 &> \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k |b_k| |z|^{k-1} \\
 &\geq |g'(z)|.
 \end{aligned}$$

Using the fact that $R(w) \geq \beta$ if and only if $|1 - \beta + w| \geq |1 + \beta - w|$, it sufficient to show that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|(1 - \beta - e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z) + (1 + e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^{n+1}(\lambda, w)f(z)| - \\
 &|(1 + \beta + e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z) - (1 + e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^{n+1}(\lambda, w)f(z)| \geq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Substituting for $D_{\alpha,\mu}^{n+1}(\lambda, w)f(z)$ and $D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z)$ in (7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &|(1 - \beta - e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z) + (1 + e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^{n+1}(\lambda, w)f(z)| \\
 &- |(1 + \beta + e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^n(\lambda, w)f(z) - (1 + e^{it})D_{\alpha,\mu}^{n+1}(\lambda, w)f(z)| \\
 &= \left| (1 - \beta - e^{it}) \left\{ z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \overline{b_k z^k} \right\} \right. \\
 &+ (1 + e^{it}) \left\{ z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^{n+1} a_k z^k \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (-1)^{n+1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^{n+1} \overline{b_k z^k} \right\} \\
 &- (1 + \beta + e^{it}) \left\{ z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \overline{b_k z^k} \right\} \\
 &\left. - (1 + e^{it}) \left\{ z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^{n+1} a_k z^k \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + (-1)^{n+1} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^{n+1} \overline{b_k z^k} \right\} \right|
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left| (2 - \beta)z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(1 - \beta - e^{it}) + (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(1 - \beta - e^{it}) - (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \overline{b_k z^k} \right| \\
 &- \left| \beta z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(1 + \beta + e^{it}) - (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(1 + \beta + e^{it}) + (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \overline{b_k z^k} \right| \\
 &= \left| (2 - \beta)z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(1 - \beta - e^{it}) + (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(\beta - 1 + e^{it}) + (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \overline{b_k z^k} \right| \\
 &- \left| \beta z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(-1 - \beta - e^{it}) + (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{(1 + \beta + e^{it}) + (1 + e^{it}) \times}{[(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]} \right\} [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \overline{b_k z^k} \right| \\
 &\geq 2(1 - \beta)|z| - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{[4k - 2\beta - 2 + 4(k - 1) - 2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)] \times}{[(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n} \right\} |a_k| |z|^k \\
 &\quad - \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{[4k + 2\beta + 2 + 4(k + 1) - 2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)] \times}{[(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n} \right\} |b_k| |z|^k \\
 &> 2(1 - \beta) \left\{ \begin{aligned} &1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} |a_k| \\ &- \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} |b_k| \end{aligned} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

This last expression is non-negative by (6), and so the proof is completed.

Theorem II.2 Let $f_n = h + \overline{g_n}$ be given by (5). Then $f_n \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ if and only if

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ [2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \right\} a_k \\
 &+ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ [2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n \right\} b_k \tag{8} \\
 &\leq (1 - \beta),
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\mu, \lambda, w \geq 0, 0 \leq \alpha \leq \mu w^\lambda, t \in R, n \in N_0, 0 \leq \beta < 1$.

Proof: The "if" part follows from theorem (6) upon nothing that $\overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta) \subset S_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$. For the "only if" part, we show that $f \notin \overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ if the condition (8) does not hold. We note that a necessary and sufficient condition for $f_n = h + \overline{g}_n$ given by (5), to be in $\overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ is that the condition (4) to be satisfied. This is equivalent to,

$$Re \left\{ \frac{(1 - \beta)z - \left[\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left([2((k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] \right) a_k z^k \right. \right.}{z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k z^k + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n b_k \bar{z}^k} \left. \left. + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left([2((k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] \right) b_k \bar{z}^k \right] \right\} \geq 0.$$

The above condition must hold for all values of $z, |z| = r < 1$. Upon choosing the value of z on the opposite real axis where $0 \leq z = r < 1$ we must have

$$Re \left\{ \frac{(1 - \beta) - \left[\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left([2((k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] \right) a_k r^{k-1} \right. \right.}{1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n a_k r^k + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n b_k r^{k-1}} \left. \left. + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left([2((k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] \right) b_k r^{k-1} \right] \right\} \geq 0. \tag{9}$$

If the condition (8) does not hold, then the numerator in (9) is negative for r sufficiently close to 1. Hence there exist $z_0 = r_0$ in $(0,1)$ for which quotient in (9) is negative. This contradicts the required condition for $\overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ and so the proof is complete.

III Distortion Inequalities and Extreme Points

In this section, we obtain extreme points for the class $\overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$.

Theorem III.1 Let $f_n \in \overline{S}_H(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$. Then for $|z| = r < 1$ we have

$$|f_n(z)| \leq (1 + b_1)r + \left\{ \frac{1 - \beta}{[2(2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} \right. \\ \left. \frac{[2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 1)) + (1 + \beta)] [2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1]^n}{[2(2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} b_1 \right\} r^2,$$

and

$$|f_n(z)| \geq (1 - b_1)r - \left\{ \frac{1 - \beta}{\left[\frac{2(2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)}{[\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} \right]} \left[\frac{2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 1)) + (1 + \beta)}{[2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1]^n} b_1 \right] \right\} r^2.$$

Proof: We only prove the right hand inequality. The proof for the left hand inequality is similar and will be omitted. Let $f_n \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$. Taking the absolute value of f_n , we have

$$\begin{aligned} |f_n(z)| &\leq (1 + b_1)r + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} (a_k + b_k)r^k \\ &\leq (1 + b_1)r + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} (a_k + b_k)r^2 \\ &= (1 + b_1)r + \left\{ \frac{(1 - \beta)r^2}{\left[\frac{2(2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)}{[\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} \right]} \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{[2(2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n}{1 - \beta} [a_k + b_k] \right\} \\ &\leq (1 + b_1)r + \frac{(1 - \beta)r^2}{[2(2 + (\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} \times \\ &\quad \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} a_k + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} b_k \right\} \\ &\leq (1 + b_1)r + \frac{(1 - \beta)}{[2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} \times \\ &\quad \left\{ 1 - \frac{[2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1) + (1 + \beta)] [2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1]^n}{1 - \beta} b_1 \right\} r^2 \\ &\leq (1 + b_1)r + \left\{ \frac{(1 - \beta)}{\left[\frac{2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)}{[\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} \right]} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{[2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1) + (1 + \beta)] [2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1]^n}{[2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha)) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} b_1 \right\} r^2. \end{aligned}$$

The following covering result follows from the left hand inequality in Theorem 3.1.

Corollary III.1 Let f_n of the form(5) be so that $f_n \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$. Then

$$\left\{ w : |w| < \left[\frac{[2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n - (1 + \beta) - \left([2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n - (1 + \beta) \right) \times [2(2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1) + (1 + \beta)] [2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + 1]^n}{[2(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2) - (1 + \beta)] [\mu w^\lambda - \alpha + 2]^n} \right] \right\} \subset f_n(U).$$

Theorem III.2 Let f_n be given by (5). Then $f_n \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ if and only if

$$f_n(z) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [X_k h_k(z) + Y_k g_{nk}(z)], \quad \text{where, } h_1(z) = z, \quad (10)$$

$$h_k(z) = z - \left\{ \frac{1 - \beta}{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n} z^k \right\}, \quad k \geq 2,$$

$$g_{nk}(z) = z + (-1)^n \left\{ \frac{1 - \beta}{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] \times [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n} z^{-k} \right\}, \quad k \geq 2,$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [X_k + Y_k] = 1, \quad X_k \geq 0, \quad Y_k \geq 0.$$

In particular, the extreme points of $\overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ are $\{h_k\}$ and $\{g_n\}$.

Proof: For function f_n of the form (10) we may write,

$$\begin{aligned} f_n(z) &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [X_k h_k(z) + Y_k g_{nk}(z)] \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [X_k + Y_k] z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1 - \beta}{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n} X_k z^k \right\} \\ &\quad + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{1 - \beta}{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n} Y_k z^{-k} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \left(\frac{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} \right) \times \right\} + \\ &\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \left(\frac{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} \right) \times \right\} \\ &\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} X_k + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} Y_k = 1 - X_1 \leq 1, \end{aligned}$$

so $f_n \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$.

Conversely, if $f_n \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$, then

$$a_k \leq \frac{1 - \beta}{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}$$

and

$$b_k \leq \frac{1 - \beta}{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}$$

setting

$$X_k = \frac{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} a_k; (k \geq 2),$$

$$Y_k = \frac{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} b_k; (k \geq 1),$$

and

$$X_1 = 1 - \left(\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} X_k + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} Y_k \right)$$

where, $X_1 \geq 0$.

$$\text{Then, } f_n(z) = X_1 z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} X_k h_k(z) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} Y_k g_{nk}(z)$$

so the proof is complete.

IV Convex Combination

In this section, we illustrate that the class $\overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ is closed with regard to convex combination of its members.

Theorem IV.1 *The class $\overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ is closed under convex combinations.*

Proof: Let $f_{n_i} \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots$, where f_{n_i} is given by

$$f_{n_i}(z) = z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_{k_i} z^k + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} b_{k_i} \bar{z}^k.$$

Then by (7),

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{[2((k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k - 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} \right\} a_{k_i} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left\{ \frac{[2((k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k + 1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} \right\} b_{k_i} \leq 1. \tag{11}$$

For $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i = 1, 0 \leq t_i \leq 1$, the convex combination of f_{n_i} may be written as

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i f_{n_i}(z) = z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i a_{k_i} \right) z^k + (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i b_{k_i} \right) z^{-k}.$$

Then by (11),

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i a_{k_i} \right) \\ & \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i b_{k_i} \right) \\ & = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i \left(\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) - (1 + \beta)] [(k-1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} a_{k_i} + \right. \\ & \quad \left. \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{[2((k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k) + (1 + \beta)] [(k+1)(\mu w^\lambda - \alpha) + k]^n}{1 - \beta} b_{k_i} \right) \\ & \leq \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i = 1. \end{aligned}$$

This is the condition required by (7) and so $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_i f_{n_i}(z) \in \overline{S_H}(\lambda, w, n, \alpha, \beta)$.

V CONCLUSION

In this paper an attempt has been made to introduce and investigate some properties for a new subclass of harmonic univalent functions by using a new differential operator. Based on this work, further useful study on different subclasses of harmonic univalent functions can be established.

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